

THE ROLE OF INNOVATION MANAGEMENT IN INCREASING ENTERPRISE COMPETITIVENESS

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Abstract: Innovation management plays an important role in increasing the competitiveness of the enterprise. Enterprises create their competitive advantages through innovation, product and service improvement, process optimization and introduction of new technologies in this area. Innovation management is also important in stimulating employee creativity, adapting to market demands, and meeting customer needs. This study presents the main principles of innovation management, its role in increasing the competitiveness of the enterprise, and practical examples.

Keywords: Innovation management, competitiveness, product innovation, process innovation, technological development, creativity, adaptation to market requirements, customer needs, strategic planning, enterprise efficiency.

Introduction. Today, the importance of innovative management to increase competitiveness in the global economy is increasing. Innovation management is the process of developing and implementing new ideas, products and processes. This article examines the role of innovation management in increasing enterprise competitiveness, its main components and practical examples.

What is Innovation Management?

Innovation management is the process of managing innovation within an organization. This process includes the following steps:

1. Idea generation: Generating new ideas and evaluating them.
2. Design: Turn ideas into practical projects.
3. Production: The process of producing new products or services.
4. Commercialization: Marketing and selling a product or service.

Competitiveness and Innovation Management:

Competitiveness is the ability of an enterprise to gain an advantage over its competitors in its field. Innovation management provides several important aspects in increasing competitiveness:

New Products and Services: With the help of innovation management, enterprises can meet market demands by developing new products and services. This will help you stand out from your competitors.

Process Improvement: Innovation helps to optimize processes and increase efficiency. This allows to reduce costs and increase profits.

Adapting to Customer Demands: Innovative management enables us to study customer needs and offer them suitable products. This increases customer loyalty.

Market Expansion: Innovation enables the opening of new markets and the expansion of existing markets. This increases the competitiveness of the enterprise.

Key Components of Innovation Management

Research and Development (R&D): One of the key components of innovation management is the process of developing and testing new ideas.

Strategic Planning: The planning process required to develop and implement innovative strategies.

Corporate Culture: Creating a corporate culture that supports and encourages innovation.

Collaboration and Networking: Collaboration with other organizations, universities and research centers in innovation processes.

Practical Examples:

Apple Inc.: Apple can be cited as an example of successful innovation management. Their iPhone, iPad and other products changed the market and gave them a huge advantage over their competitors.

Tesla: Tesla cars have increased their competitiveness by introducing innovative technologies. Their electric cars and autonomous driving technologies have transformed the market.

Innovative management plays an important role in increasing the competitiveness of the enterprise. By developing new products and services, improving processes, adapting to customer requirements, and expanding the market, businesses will be able to differentiate themselves from their competitors. In order to successfully implement innovation management, it is necessary to focus on key components such as research and development, strategic planning, corporate culture and collaboration.

Conclusion. Innovative management is an important tool for increasing competitiveness for enterprises. It helps not only to create new products and services, but also to improve existing processes. Through innovative approaches,

enterprises will be able to quickly adapt to market requirements, meet customer needs and stand out from competitors. Also, innovative management helps to stimulate the creativity of employees and develop an innovative culture within the enterprise. As a result, innovative management serves to increase the overall efficiency of the enterprise and strengthen its competitiveness.

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